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Tool for interpretation of RRM in biophysical space

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The RNAct project

RNAct is a EU-MSCA ITN project with as research aim the design of novel **RNA recognition motif (RRM)** proteins for exploitation in synthetic biology and bio-analytics. We use **computational approaches** to analyse proteins and RNA, and test newly designed RRM in large-scale experiments. Viable RRM are studied with integrative **structural biology**, and will be applied in **synthetic biology** and in **bio-analytics**.

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About this document

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Table of Contents

List of Tables	4
List of Figures	5
List of Acronyms.....	6
Summary.....	7
1. Software overview	8
1.1 Code structure.....	8
2. User input and processing	9
2.1 Biophysical effect of point mutations.....	9
2.1.1 Mutagenicity tool.....	9
2.1.2 qBLAST	10
2.2 Biophysical comparison of RRM families	10
2.2.1 MSA alignment.....	10
3. Biophysical predictions	11
3.1 Implemented tools.....	11
3.2 Output.....	12
4. RRM families data storage	13
5. Conclusions	14
References	15

List of Tables

Table 1: RRM Pfam IDs, family names and the number of sequences for each seed alignment [6].....	13
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List of Figures

Figure 1: Schematic view of the code structure for the two main features of this software. .8	
Figure 2: RNA-binding protein Musashi homolog 1 (UniProt Id: Q61474) backbone dynamics prediction for BLAST results (blue) and the mutated sequence G150A (red).....11	
Figure 3: Schematic view of the biophysical prediction output, the distribution values stored and how it translates into the final results plot.12	
Figure 4: Coil propensities for the PF09162 and PF00076 RRMA Pfam families.....14	

List of Acronyms

Abbreviation/ acronym	Description
RRM	RNA Recognition Motif
MSA	Multiple Sequence Alignment
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
T-Coffee	Tree-based Consistency Objective Function For Alignment Evaluation
PPII	Polyproline II helix
Pfam	Protein family database

Summary

This deliverable describes the tool for interpretation of RRM in biophysical space. For that purpose, two main features have been implemented in this software:

1) Biophysical effect of point mutations: This feature allows the user to input a target protein sequence, generate a mutated sequence and compare the biophysical predictions with a multiple sequence alignment obtained through BLAST, to gain a wider perspective of the mutation effect.

2) Biophysical comparison of MSAs: By aligning two different MSAs among themselves, they can be biophysically compared. The MSA source might be, for instance, a protein family alignment or a set of related sequences. For this approach the results of all the 15 RRM protein families available from PFAM have been stored.

In both cases the distribution of the biophysical predictions for all the sequences in the MSA indicates where the biophysical behaviour within the protein family is conserved (or not) for particular protein regions, so establishing an evolutionary allowed range for these features. Point mutations that move out of this range would therefore be expected to disrupt the biophysical properties of the protein, and are more likely to interfere with its functionality.

1. Software overview

1.1 Code structure

The tool for interpretation of RRM in biophysical space is organised as follows, with indication of the two main features (effect of point mutation or comparison between two protein families):

Figure 1: Schematic view of the code structure for the two main features of this software.

The software is executed from the terminal and the selected feature depends on the arguments provided as explained below in the main script (*main.py*) help message:

```
$ python main.py -h
usage: main.py [-h] [-fasta FASTA] [-align ALIGN ALIGN]

Input handler
optional arguments:
  -h, --help            Show this help message and exit
  -fasta FASTA          The input protein sequence/s in fasta format to run
                        qBLAST and the biophysical predictors
  -align ALIGN ALIGN    MSA files to be aligned and biophysically compared
```

The code is available in an open access repository so the scientific community can use it (<https://bitbucket.org/bio2byte/seqrrm/src/master/>). Details about the requirements and installation are on the *readme.md* file.

2. User input and processing

There are two kinds of inputs that can be provided depending on the analysis to perform. For the biophysical effect of point mutations, a file with a single protein sequence must be given, then the mutated sequence is generated through the terminal and qBLAST [1] is run in parallel. All the sequences are then aligned, their biophysical properties are predicted and the results are visualised. For the MSAs biophysical comparison, two MSA files must be provided, they are aligned, and the biophysical properties are predicted and finally plotted to compare both MSAs. The input handling differs between both approaches while the biophysical predictor and plotting functionalities remain mostly the same.

2.1 Biophysical effect of point mutations

This approach allows the user to check the effect of a point mutation on the target protein comparing it with the predictions over an MSA obtained using BLAST. The input must be the protein sequence in *FASTA* format. Once the input is provided and the script has run, it will ask for a filename to save the results, which will be saved under the results folder.

2.1.1 Mutagenicity tool

Once the results filename is given, the protein sequence from the input file will be displayed in the terminal and it will ask for; (1) the residue position to mutate, (2) the residue to mutate it to, as it is shown in the terminal in the example below, where the filename used is *test*, the residue to mutate is *glycine 150* and it is mutated to an *alanine*.

```
$ python main.py -fasta data_test_cases/Q61474.fasta
```

```
Write the output filename for the BLAST results (String without extension nor spaces):
```

```
>>>test
```

```
Select one position in the sequence to mutate:
```

```
METDAPQPGLASPDSPHPCKMFIGGLSWQTTQEGLREYFGQFGEVKECLVMRDPLTKRSRGFGFVTFMDQAGVDKVLAQ
SRHELDSKTIDPKVAFPRRAQPKMVTRTKKIFVGGLSVNTTVEDVKHYFEQFGKVDDAMLMFDKTTNRHRGFGFVTFESE
DIVEKVCEIHFHEINNMVECKKAQPKEVMSPTGSARGRSRVMPYGMDFMLGIGMLGYPGFQATTYASRSYTG LAPGYT
YQFPEFRVERSPLPSAPVLPeltaIPLTAYGPMAAAAAAAAAVVRGTGSHPWMTAPPPGSTPSRTGGFLGTTSPGPMAELY
GAANQDSGVSSYISAASPAPSTGFGHSLGGPLIATAFTNGYH
```

```
>>>150
```

```
You have selected G150 to mutate
```

```
Select the residue to mutate to:
```

```
A, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, K, L, M, N, P, Q, R, S, T, V, W, Y
```

```
>>>A
```

2.1.2 qBLAST

For this feature BLAST is implemented through qBLAST using the Biopython's Blast package [1]. It is an online version of BLAST where only three arguments are required to run it (listed below). This was performed using the `run_qblast()` python function below:

- **BLAST program:** `blastp` because the input is a protein sequence
- **Database:** `refseq_protein`
- **Target sequence:** From the *FASTA* input file

```
def run_qblast(self, blast_prog='blastp', db='refseq_protein'):
    fasta_string = open(self.rnm_seq).read()
    result_handle = NCBIWWW.qblast(blast_prog, db, fasta_string,
                                   format_type='XML')

    with open("{}".format(self.file_name), "w") as out_handle:
        out_handle.write(result_handle.read())

    self.parse_blast(self.file_name)
```

When the run is completed the results are outputted in XML format and the sequences are parsed and filtered by another function according to their e-value, identity and coverage with respect to the target sequence, using the following thresholds:

- e-value < 0.04
- Sequence identity > 0.9
- Sequence coverage > 0.9

By using these thresholds, we ensure that the final sequences cannot be obtained by chance (low e-value), and they are similar to the target protein both in sequence (high identity) and length (high coverage). The final set of sequences is appended to the original target sequence and the mutated one. All of them are then aligned using T-Coffee [2] with default settings, the output is an MSA in *FASTA* format used by the biophysical predictor afterwards.

2.2 Biophysical comparison of RRM families

This feature allows the user to compare the biophysical predictions of two MSAs from distinct RRM families (or any other MSA of related sequences). The inputs are the two MSAs in any supported format by T-Coffee (*aln*, *MSF*, *PIR* and *FASTA*).

2.2.1 MSA alignment

Both inputted MSAs are then aligned using T-Coffee with the *-profile* option that allows to quickly align two or more MSAs. The results are now outputted in *aln* format (Clustal standard). The source of the original sequences is stored in a python dictionary to properly plot the results when the biophysical predictions are calculated.

3. Biophysical predictions

The biophysical predictor class it takes all the sequences from the MSAs, runs the predictions individually for every sequence, and finally maps the results back to the original MSA. It works exactly the same way for both approaches, being the only difference that for the point mutation feature only one MSA is provided corresponding to the BLAST results and the target and mutated sequences, while for the RRM family comparison it runs also for a single MSA but it has to be mapped to the two original MSAs afterwards.

3.1 Implemented tools

Several biophysical predictors were implemented within this software, belonging to 4 different main groups:

- **DynaMine** [3]: Backbone and sidechain dynamics
- **DisoMine** [4][5]: Protein disorder
- **EFoldMine** [4]: Early folding regions
- **Secondary structure propensities** [4]: Helix, sheet, coil and polyproline II helix (ppII) propensities.

These predictors provide important information to better understand the behaviour of these proteins. Moreover, the fact that are run over an MSA from a protein family or BLAST results, allows a wider interpretation of the results showing the evolutionary allowed range. Then in the point mutation approach we can check whether the mutated sequence is outside of that range or not (Figure 2).

Figure 2: RNA-binding protein Musashi homolog 1 (UniProt Id: Q61474) backbone dynamics prediction for BLAST results (blue) and the mutated sequence G150A (red).

3.2 Output

The final output of the biophysical prediction class is a file for each MSA with the distribution of the 8 biophysical properties prediction mentioned above (Figure 3). The results with the aligned sequences are stored in a *json* file under the *results/* folder using the filename inputted by the user ending with “*_preds_distrib.json*”.

The distribution values stored for every position in the alignment can be plotted as the example shown in Figure 2 (the user selects which biophysical property to plot), also shown in the schematic Figure 3 for a better understanding. The stored values are; (a) top outlier, (b) 75 percentile, (c) median value of the predictions, (d) 25 percentile and (e) bottom outlier. In the point mutation approach, the prediction for the mutated sequence is represented with a thin red line (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Schematic view of the biophysical prediction output, the distribution values stored and how it translates into the final results plot.

Visualise the distribution values of the predictions allows to quickly identify which sections of the alignment are more or less conserved and find key regions in the protein sequence/structure where the differences in the biophysical behaviour leads, for instance, to differences in their binding with the RNA.

4. RRM families data storage

There are 15 different RRM families in the Pfam database (Table 1). All these families were validated by Hrishikesh Dhondge (ESR3) and added in Inter3M, the RNAct database, and selected from there for their interpretation in the biophysical space.

Table 1: RRM Pfam IDs, family names and the number of sequences for each seed alignment [6].

Pfam Id	Family name	Sequences in the seed alignment
PF00076	RRM_1	72
PF08777	RRM_3	11
PF13893	RRM_5	7
PF16367	RRM_7	14
PF11835	RRM_8	10
PF18444	RRM_9	36
PF16842	RRM_occluded	49
PF09162	Tap-RNA_bind	62
PF05172	Nup35_RRM	7
PF02994	Transposase_22	2
PF17799	RRM_Rrp7	9
PF03880	DbpA	606
PF17774	YlmH_RBD	88
PF08675	RNA_bind	11
PF03468	XS	82

For every Pfam family the seed alignment was downloaded, that is a manually verified alignment for a representative set of sequences for that family [6]. The number of sequences included on each seed alignment is on Table 5 alongside with the Id of the Pfam family and the family name.

All these alignments were compared with each other in pairs, and the biophysical properties predicted, storing all the obtained results. For each MSA comparison the distribution of the predictions is stored in a *json* file with the alignment of a single family, the naming of the files uses the following format; *PfamId1_seed_aligned_to_pfamId2_seed_preds_distrib.json*, being *PfamId1* the name of the family the data corresponds to, and *PfamId2* the Id of the family the alignment has been done with. All this data was stored under *rrm_pfam_data/pairwise_pfam_alignment_distrib/* folder (210 files) and all the associated graphs for each biophysical property comparison in the *graphs/* subfolder (840 files).

One example about the kind of plots generated for the biophysical comparison can be found in the Figure 4, for the comparison between the PF09162 and PF00076 RRM families in terms of coil propensity. In most of the positions the propensities follow a similar trend, but around the position 40 in the alignment we have a remarkable difference. The PF09162 is much more conserved than the other one (even though the MSA consists of 62 sequences), and has a significantly lower coil propensity.

Figure 4: Coil propensities for the PF09162 and PF00076 RRMA Pfam families.

The accessibility to the data allows to easily compare the Pfam families as in the example, and spot key regions of the sequences to better understand their behaviour.

5. Conclusions

This software provides an easy way to interpret the RRM in biophysical space, with a functionality to test the effect of point mutations and how it differs from the evolutionary allowed observed behaviour as extracted from MSAs based on BLAST searches. In addition, it contains a feature to biophysically compare two different MSAs, so enabling the identification of key regions in the protein with similar or different behaviour, which can help to understand their behaviour. As a near future perspective, we will also add information from structure-based alignments when the structure is available, gaining more information from the structural perspective.

The software has been very useful for the gathering of RRM biophysical information, as all the results for the 15 different RRM Pfam families are now stored. This tool is, however, not limited to RRMs, and can also be applied to any other kind of target proteins or protein families to perform a quick analysis of their biophysical space.

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